

IKKI O'ZGARUVCHILI TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASI

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ABSTRACT

Maqolada ikki o'zgaruvchili tenglamalar sistemasi, uni yechishning Kramer usullari o'rganilgan..

Ikki o'zgaruvchili tenglamalar sistemasi, matematikda, texnikada va boshqa sohalar bo'yicha juda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ikki o'zgaruvchili tenglamalar sistemasi, har bir x qiymatiga mos keladigan y qiymatlarini hisoblash uchun amalga oshiriladi. Bu, grafiklar, ko'ordinatalar va Kramer usuli orqali ham yoritilishi mumkin.

Bunday tenglamalar sistemasining umumiy ko'rinishi

$$\begin{cases} a_1x + b_1y = c_1 \\ a_2x + b_2y = c_2 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

dan iborat bo'lib, u *ikki noma'lum (o'zgaruvchanli) chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi* deb ataladi.

1-ta'rif. x va y o'zgaruvchilarning (2) sistemaning har bir tenglamasini to'g'ri sonli tenglikka aylantiruvchi α va β qiymatlari jufti (α, β) uning *yechimi* deyiladi. (2) sistemani yechish uchun uning birinchi tenglamasini b_2 ga, ikkinchisini b_1 ga ko'paytirib, ularni ayiramiz. U holda

$x(a_1b_2 - a_2b_1) = c_1b_2 - c_2b_1$ hosil bo'ladi, agar $a_1b_2 - a_2b_1 \neq 0$ bo'lsa,

$$x = \frac{c_1b_2 - c_2b_1}{a_1b_2 - a_2b_1} \quad (2)$$

ga ega bo'lamiz.

$$y = \frac{a_1c_2 - a_2c_1}{a_1b_2 - a_2b_1} \quad (3)$$

ni topamiz.

Shunday qilib, $a_1b_2 - a_2b_1 \neq 0$ bo'lsa, (1) sistema yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi. Ushbu

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

ko'rinishdagi jadval 2 sistemaning *matritsasi* deyiladi. A matritsaning gorizontal qatorlari uning *satrlari*, vertikal qatorlari esa - *ustunlari* deyiladi. a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2 lar uning *elementlari* deyiladi. Qaralayotgan matritsa, *ikkinchi tartibli kvadrat matritsa* deyiladi. Uning chap yuqori burchagidan o'ng pastki burchagiga boruvchi diogonal uning bosh dioganali deyiladi.

3 va 4 formulardagi kasrlarning maxraji bosh dioganaldagi elementlar ko'paytmasidan, ikkinchi dioganalda turgan elementlarning ko'paytmasini ayirish natijasida tuzilganligi ko'rinib turibdi: $a_1b_2 - a_2b_1$. Bu ifoda A matritsaning *determinanti* deb ataladi va quyidagicha belgilanadi:

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

Demak, ta'rifga ko'ra,

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_1b_2 - a_2b_1$$

Quyidagicha tasdiq o'rinli: ikkinchi tartibli determinant nolga teng bo'lishi uchun, uning satrlaridagi yoki ustunlaridagi elementlar proporsional bo'lishi zarur va yetarli.

Yuqoridagi belgilashlar asosida 3 tenglikning surati quyidagi determinantdan iborat:

$$\Delta_1 = \begin{vmatrix} c_1 & b_1 \\ c_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} = c_1b_2 - c_2b_1.$$

Bu determinant Δ determinantdagi birinchi ustunni ozod hadlar ustuni bilan almashtirishdan hosil qilingan. Xuddi shunga o'xshash Δ determinantning ikkinchi ustunini ozod hadlar bilan almashtirsak, 4 tenglikning suratidagi ifoda hosil bo'ladi:

$$\Delta_2 = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & c_1 \\ a_2 & c_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_1c_2 - a_2c_1$$

Shunday qilib, agar $\Delta \neq 0$ bo'lsa, 2 sistemaning yechimi $x = \frac{\Delta_1}{\Delta}$, $y = \frac{\Delta_2}{\Delta}$

lardan iborat va yagonadir. Bu formulalar Kramer formulalari deyiladi.

Misol. Kramer formulalaridan foydalanib, 1 sistemani yechamiz.

$$\begin{cases} x + y = 20 \\ 4x + 2y = 76, \end{cases} \quad \Delta = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 4 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 1 \cdot 2 - 4 \cdot 1 = -2 \neq 0$$

$$\Delta_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 20 & 1 \\ 76 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 20 \cdot 2 - 76 \cdot 1 = -36; \quad \Delta_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 20 \\ 4 & 76 \end{vmatrix} = 76 \cdot 1 - 20 \cdot 4 = -4.$$

U holda, $x = (-36) : (-2) = 18$, $y = (-4) : (-2) = 2$.

Endi

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_1b_2 - a_2b_1 = 0 \quad (4)$$

holni qaraymiz. 5 tenglikni $\frac{a_1}{a_2} = \frac{b_1}{b_2}$ ko'rinishda yozish mumkin, ya'ni bu holda

noma'lumlarning koeffitsentlari proporsionaldir.

Bundan tashqari, agar

$$\begin{vmatrix} c_1 & b_1 \\ c_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 \text{ ya'ni } \frac{c_1}{c_2} = \frac{b_1}{b_2}$$

ham o'rinli bo'lsa,

$$\frac{a_1}{a_2} = \frac{b_1}{b_2} = \frac{c_1}{c_2}$$

bo'lib, biz ikki noma'lumli bitta tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz. Bu holda u sistema *cheksiz ko'p* yechimga ega bo'ladi.

Nihoyat, agar

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 \text{ lekin, } \begin{vmatrix} c_1 & b_1 \\ c_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} \neq 0 \text{ bo'lsa,}$$

ya'ni

$$\frac{a_1}{a_2} = \frac{b_1}{b_2} \neq \frac{c_1}{c_2}$$

bo'lsa, u holda sistema ziddiyatli bo'ladi va yechimga ega bo'lmaydi.

1- sistemaning $x = \alpha, y = \beta$ yechimi Dekart koordinatalari sistemasida $a_1x + b_1y = c_1$ va $a_2x + b_2y = c_2$ to'g'ri chiziqlarning kesishish nuqtasini ifodalaydi.

Agar $\begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix} \neq 0$ bo'lsa, to'g'ri chiziqlar har xil bo'lib, yagona umumiy nuqtaga ega

bo'ladi. $\frac{a_1}{a_2} = \frac{b_1}{b_2} = \frac{c_1}{c_2}$ bo'lsa, har ikkala tenglama bitta tenglamani ifodalaydi va uning har bir

nuqtasi, berilgan to'g'ri chiziqning «kesishish nuqtalari» bo'ladi, ya'ni ular ustma-ust tushadi.

Nihoyat, agar $\frac{a_1}{a_2} = \frac{b_1}{b_2} \neq \frac{c_1}{c_2}$ bo'lsa, to'g'ri chiziqlar parallel va ular bitta ham umumiy nuqtaga

ega bo'lmaydi.

Shuni ta'kidlab o'tamizki, maktab matematika kursida 2 sistemani o'rniga qo'yish va qo'shish usullari yordamida yechilar edi. Bu yerda yana bitta usulni o'rgandik. Ushbu usulning bitta qulayligi shundaki, uning yordamida n noma'lumli n -ta chizikli tenglamalar sistemasini ham yechish mumkin. Bunga qiziqqan o'quvchilar [1] adabiyotga murojaat qilishlari mumkin.

Umuman, $f(x, y) = 0$ va $\varphi(x, y) = 0$ tenglamalar sistemasi deb, ularning $(f(x, y) = 0) \wedge (\varphi(x, y) = 0)$ kon'yunksiyasiga, maktabda belgilangandek,

$$\begin{cases} f(x, y) = 0 \\ \varphi(x, y) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

sistemaga aytiladi. 6 sistemaning har birini to'g'ri sonli tenglikka aylantiruvchi α va β sonlar jufti (α, β) uning *yechimi* deyiladi.

Bizga ma'lumki, ikki predikat kon'yunksiyasining rostlik to'plami, shu predikatlar rostlik to'plamlari kesishmasidan iborat. Xuddi shunga o'xshash 6 sistema yechimlarining

to'plami, $f(x, y) = 0$ va $\varphi(x, y) = 0$ tenglamalar yechimlari to'plamining kesishmasidan iborat. Geometrik yo'l bilan bu to'plam quyidagicha topiladi: $f(x, y) = 0$ va $\varphi(x, y) = 0$ tenglamalarning grafigi chiziladi, so'ngra bu grafiklarning kesishish nuqtalari topiladi.

Misol. $(4; 3)$, $(-4; -3)$ juftliklar

$$\begin{cases} 3x - 4y = 0 \\ x^2 + y^2 = 25 \end{cases}$$

sistema yechimlari to'plamiga tegishli bo'ladi. Haqiqatdan, $x = 4, y = 3$ hamda $x = -4, y = -3$ lar tenglamalarning har birini qanoatlantiradi:

$$3 \cdot 4 - 4 \cdot 3 = 0, 4^2 + 3^2 = 25. \text{ va}$$

$$3 \cdot (-4) - 4 \cdot (-3) = 0, (-4)^2 + (-3)^2 = 25$$

Berilgan sistema boshqa yechimlarga ega emasligini ko'rsatish mumkin. Sistema yechi-mini grafik tasvirlaymiz. Sistemaning birinchi tenglamasining grafigi to'g'ri chiziq, ikkinchisidiki esa markazi koor-dinata boshida va radiusi 5 ga teng bo'lgan aylana. Ular $A(4, 3)$ va $B(-4, -3)$ nuqtalarda kesishadi.

Bunday sistemalar, statistik hisob-kitoblarda, matematik modellarda, injenerlik amaliyotlarda, kriptografiyada, hisoblash texnologiyalarida va boshqalar kabi ko'plab sohalarda foydalaniladi.

INNOVATIVE ACADEMY

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